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הפקולטה להנדסה
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Attack Angle Influence on Growth Efficiency of Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes

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Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes: Highly useful for Composite Materials

- Carbon nanotubes (CNT) have exceptional properties.
- Vertically aligned CNT (VACNT) retain anisotropic transport properties.
- Due to VACNT high porosity, immense surface is available for applications.

Property	Single-walled	Double-walled	Multiwalled
	carbon nanotube	carbon nanotube	carbon nanotube
Tensile strength (GPa)	50–100	23–63	10–60
Elastic modulus (TPa)	1	–	0.3–1
Elongation at break (%)	5.8	28	–
Density (g/cm ³)	1.3–1.5	1.5	1.8–2.0
Electric conductivity (S/m)	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶
Thermal conductivity at room temperature (W/m K)	6000	3000	2000

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2017.08.020>

VACNT Synthesis: Chemical Vapor Deposition

Rovinsky *et al.* - 10.1021/acsnm.0c02681

Taller VACNT reduces prominence of CNT-CNT contacts, weak links, both mechanically and electrically.

VACNT Synthesis and Challenges: Carbon Feeding Difference

- Different regions on the sample grow at different rates.
- Above certain heights, this becomes apparent and causes sinking.
- Extreme sinking results in the collapse of the sample centers.
- We started looking for an explanation.
- Can you help us?

Computational Fluid Dynamics

- A branch of finite-element analysis (FEA) deals with the movement and interaction of fluids. Gases are considered fluids.
- The fluid velocity during VACNT CVD was simulated in several times along the growth process.
- My assumptions (first-order approximation):
 - Inert (physical) flow, disregard heat and mass transfer.
 - Rigid sample, disregard porous structure.
 - Fluid properties are C_2H_4 .

Methodology: CFD/Real-life CVD Hybrid

CFD Results

$$\delta = 99\% \cdot U_{\infty}$$

Assumed Phenomenon: Separation bubble

- The inbound flow traps a vortex on the surface, which decreases the growth rate in the middle of the sample.
- Higher step – larger trapped vortex.
- The angle decreases the dimensions of the trapped vortex.

In VACNT case:

CFD Results – Attack Angle

- In an effort to reduce boundary layer thickness, the concept of attack angles was introduced.

Quartz Substrate Jigs:

- Designed dedicated jigs with attack angles, so that the substrate would be at an angle.

Gig Generation 1

Gig Generation 2

Substrate

Jig

Height of VACNT as $f(\theta)$, as $f(\text{growth } t)$

- Clear correlation between attack θ and sample height.
- Interestingly, best results are 25° , while in the simulations its 20° .

Conclusions

- The effectiveness of fluid dynamics becomes noticeable when 'pushing the envelope' of nanofabrication.
- VACNT samples' centers sink, and even collapse during fabrication.
- CFD show barrier layer thickness increases as function of sample height.
- Some attack angles show decrease in the barrier layer thickness.
- VACNT sample height enhanced with attack angle.